

Exposing Ghost Workers in Nigeria: An Emerging Ethical Dimension to Get Things Right

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Abstract

The nature and character exhibited by Post-Colonial system of Nigerian Public Service has been characterized by bloated number of ghost workers who receive their salaries and other emoluments at the end of the month. There tend to be dramatic turn by the government at various levels to fish-out the cankerworm which has eaten deep into the fabrics of the government. The introduction of the integrated personnel payroll and information system by the federal government and computerization exercise by the state government is a significant tool to put to death the menace of ghost workers syndrome in Nigeria. The paper seeks to investigate whether the integrated personnel payroll and information system has implicated the payroll fraud in Nigeria, using Enugu State as a case study. In other words, the paper ethically investigated the extent to which the State government has utilized the IPPIS in its planning and budgeting. Qualitative and quantitative methods were adequately utilized in generating its data, while the theoretical frame work of analysis was anchored on the Marxist theory of Post-Colonial state. The findings revealed that the introduction of IPPIS and computerization exercise has ethically exposed and blocked the holes through which the state treasuries were siphoned and it has also enhanced quality planning and budgeting in the Enugu State.

Keywords: *Biometric Verification Number (BVN), Enugu State, Ethics, Ghost Workers, Integrated Personnel Payroll and Information System (IPPIS), Planning and Budgeting.*

Introduction

The public service has played a very unique role in the transition of the state to achieve its philosophies. The premium attached on the public service has been the tremendous roles it always stands out to achieve. It always ensures the continuity of the government. The public service can therefore be described as a corrective of party government. This arises out of the fact that the concern of the civil service is for the good of the nation as a whole, irrespective of the political party in power. Its task is to lay the national point of view before each minister that comes. In this way, the civil service observes strict political neutrality, while ensuring the continuity of policy based on overall national interest (Adebayo, 2004:93).

However, the institutionalization of public service in Nigeria has legal and constitutional backings. It was the 1960 constitution that brought about a federal system founded on parliamentary executive. It is important to recast that immediately after the independence, the aspirations and expectations of the citizens from the new independent government were quite high and the politicians were enthusiastic to satisfy the citizen's high hopes and expectations, but this requires among others virile, strong and effective administrators (Ogunna, 1999: 57-68).

High level of corruption that has eaten deep in to the Nigeria system. This situation has also been extended to the state governments where the rate of cartel of ghost workers has increased unabated. It is important to appreciate that following the introduction of the integrated personnel payroll and information system (IPPIS) and computerization exercise by the state government at different times had revealed a huge sum of naira which were plunged and siphoned by the ghost workers. Many at times, it is argued that the rate of ghost workers in the state's vouchers were made possible by inordinate desperation of the political class and the highly placed public servants who prepare the monthly voucher and submit for remuneration of the workers.

However, it is in lieu of the above backdrop that the study sets to appreciate and investigates the extent of integrated personnel payroll and information system in curbing the menace of ghost workers in Enugu State and government utilization of IPPIS in planning and budgeting within the period of the research.

It is an attempt to address the above identified challenges and menace that the study seeks provokes and interrogates the following research questions:

- I. Does the implementation of the integrated personnel payroll and information system implicate the payroll frauds in Enugu State?
- II. How has Enugu State government utilized the integrated personnel payroll and information system in its planning and budgeting?

The appreciation of e-governance at various levels of government in Nigeria has increased the awareness and exposed the activities of government to the citizens. There is an irony of situation whereby instead of the machinery of the state

to protect the interests of the citizens, it has been compromised and serves as a tool for the enrichment of the highly placed officials at the detriment of the citizens it assumes to protect and serve.

This paper examines the integrated personnel payroll and information system and ghost worker cartel in the Enugu State. Its specific objectives are:

1. To examine whether the implementation of the integrated personnel payroll and information system has implicated payroll frauds in Enugu State.
2. To investigate whether Enugu State government has utilized the integrated personnel payroll and information system in her planning and budgeting.

REVISITING THE CONCEPT OF IPPIS

This paper investigates whether the implementation of the Integrated Personnel Payroll and Information System (IPPIS) has helped in curtailing the payroll frauds and how IPPIS has helped the state in its planning and budgeting. Based on these, the paper employed a thematic approach on review of appropriate of literature as organized under the followings:

Integrated Personnel Payroll and Biometric Regime in the Public Sectors

The recent developments in the field of science and technology have attracted myriad interests from different quarters of the society. The scientific application of electronic and other software packages had been appreciated by various tiers of government to curtail the menace of ghost workers in their payrolls. However, the most challenging variable in the system of governance remains the inability of the governments at their respective levels to know accurately the strength of staff and who receives salaries and other emoluments as at when due. The inability of the governments especially the state government before now to determine and know the accurate number of its personnel is a thing not laughable and call for the implementation of IPPIS.

Accordingly, Enakirerhi and Temile, (2007) they see the construct of integrated personnel payroll and information system as one of the strategic implementation of the federal government of Nigeria to digitalize the manual based and files system marred with corruption, inefficiency and inaccuracy of number of personnel on the service Nigeria state. Here, the authors construed the system as one among other tools used to control the tendencies of corruption in the public offices. Criticizing the definition they failed to identify and compare the old system used with the recent introduction of IPPIS.

Furthermore, Mede (2016) maintained that the reformation of the civil service, transparency and accountability, elimination of payroll frauds of public service is the fundamental objective behind the introduction of IPPIS. It adequately widened the employment opportunities and generation for the teeming population of unemployed graduates and school leavers. However, corroborating the fundamental philosophies of integrated personnel payroll and information system Idris, Adaya and Audu (2015), Uzochukwu(2015) and Hall and Torington(1998) maintained IPPIS has continued to increase efficiency in transacting government businesses, enhances confidence in payroll costs and budgeting, greatly improve management reporting and information, rebuilding public confidence, provides opportunities for an improved infrastructural facilities, creates conducive work atmosphere and job security.

However, an empirical investigation on the importance of IPPIS portrayed that the administration of President Muhammadu Buhari has taken the centre stage with the mandate of propagating transparency, accountability and probity in the public service of the federation (Enakirerhi & Temile, 2017). Replicating the fight against corruption at the state level, the Governor of Enugu State, Hon. Ifeanyi Ugwuanyi has appointed a committee charged with financial intelligence through the application of Integrated Personnel in the seventeen local government council areas. Scientific records had it that after the IPPIS and computerize biometric exercise at the different local governments revealed the total number of ghost workers uncovered, nearly 4,000 and this would have saved the State about ₦161,494,570 monthly or ₦1.938Billion annually. (Premium Times Nigeria, 2017)

However, appreciating the workings of IPPIS is the co-variable factor of biometric technology. Biometric technology is an essential tool for accuracy and accountability in the public sector. Biometrics is automated methods of captured an individual based on the physiological and morphological variables. The data capturing through biometric include the fingerprint, face, geometry, iris, retina and other vital characteristics of the individual. (Eya, 2017) Accordingly, Jay and Dunphy, (2009) they maintained that system of biometric is not a new technological development. However, tracing the origin, they argued that the ancient Egyptians used bodily characteristics to identify workers to make sure they do not claim more provision in a very corrupt ways. Also, the Chinese merchants in the late fourteenth and early

fifteenth centuries adequately used the crude method of identification. They used Palm and foot prints to identify their children.

In the recent time, the need to remove the ghost workers that had plunged the service of government at different levels, has increased in substantial importance over the years due to the consequence of unabated proliferation of staff strength of public service. According to Eya(2017); Bovens(2005) they maintained that some people object at the mention of biometric system which scans fingerprints, but for the most part, people now had understood that biometrics actually protect their privacy and that in most biometric applications, their fingerprints are not stored anywhere and their fingerprints can never be recreated from the encrypted digital template.

Furthermore, appraising the systems of IPPIS and Biometrics, Idris, Adaja and Audu(2015) stressed that the Nigerian minister of finance in February, 2011 revealed that the pilot implementation of the integrated personnel and payroll and information system in sixteen (16) Ministries, Departments and Agencies saved the nation over ₦12 billion between 2007 and to 2010. The Honourable Finance Minister in 2014 observed that as part of measure aimed at cushioning the effect of dwindling oil revenue accruing to the government resulting to thirty (30) percent fall in the price of oil in international market, the government saved 160 billion naira by weeding out 60,000 ghost workers from the payroll. (Daily Sun, 2016)

It is important to recall the press briefing of the trade union chairman of Rivers State, Comrade Onuegbu. He commended the efforts of government on different levels in its quest to combat the menace of ghost worker through the instrumentation of biometric and computerization to enhance the federal government scheme of IPPIS. He continued by saying that various State government and federal agencies have discovered ghost worker in their payroll through the implementation of biometric. He noted that ghost workers are a huge fraud that cuts across the states and the federal government had saved several billions of naira monthly from the weeding of the ghost workers in the MDAs. He acclaimed:

“For instance, the Rivers State Universal Basic Education Board recently announced that it saved the state ₦200 million monthly. With the removal of 1,477 ghost workers discovered through the use of biometric technology on the Board’s Payroll”(Onuegbu, 2015).

However, the menace of frauds in the states especially in Enugu has calls for an alarm. Therefore, following the just concluded verification exercise and computerization, it was discovered that each council of the seventeen local governments had always engaged themselves in different forms of frauds ranging from bloated number of ghost workers, falsification of certificates and birth records and to the extent of sifting of primary schools that cannot be found. It is unfortunate that our political leaders know all these but keep quite because they are at the receiving and of their percentages. The surprising thing is that, some dead persons who served the government over the decades were seen collecting their salaries and leave allowances, when the relations of the deceased do not know that their brother is or sister’s death benefits are being siphon by the political and administrative scavengers.

Planning, Budgeting and Cost of Governance in Nigeria

It is a known fact that organizational receipts and expenditures within the fiscal year determine the rate of socio-economic and infrastructural development in the state. It is when the total expenditures of the state exceed her total receipts that development starts to suffer. This scenario calls for proper planning and budgeting by the government. Here, there is the need for total overhauling of the organization activities including the personnel and its strength. In the contemporary federating states of Nigeria, the poor planning and budgeting by the government has marred the developmental strides and has constituted a serious cost of governance.

However, the phenomenon of ghost worker has undermined governmental planning and budgeting and in the long run, bloated the cost of governance in Nigeria and Enugu State in particular. Here, the cost of governance is the money spent on administrative process of the state in answering its continuous existence. It is any expenditure in maintaining government administrative structure (Fluvian, 2006). According to Eme and Ogbochie, (2013), Drucker,(2007) cost of governance is government budget allocated to both capital and recurrent expenditures on maintaining government administrative structure, which appears to be very enormous in Africa. No wonder, Afolugbe etal,(2004) construes cost of governance of the state as the total cost incurred in running the government. It is the cost of performing political duties and discharging civil services to the public (Eme and Ogbochie,(2013).

Still on the concept of cost of governance in Nigeria, a larger than optimal civil service dominated mainly by that section of the country with significant human capital deficiencies is bound to raise governance costs and institutionalized the mechanism for rent extraction (Iyoha and Oriakhi, 2002).

However, in order to appreciate the costs of governance more, it will be vital to quote Fafowora who posited that;

“When he joined the Western Region civil service as an administrative Officer in 1964 after his graduation from the then University, College, Ibadan, there were only four of them, administrative officers in the ministry of Trade to which he was posted. Today, they probably not less than 20 administrative officers doing what only four officers handled in that ministry. This back ground is necessary to fully understand and appreciate the source or sources of the huge bureaucracy that has emerged in Nigeria and the costs involved in running such a vast bureaucracy” (Fafowora, 2011).

However, the above quote could be attributed to the high incidence of ghost worker cartel which is predominant in Nigeria’s political system. The scenario which has been created is that the fiscal budget as a result of planning by the state cannot be effectively utilized due to high number of public servants who are ghost workers. In Enugu State, the total amount of money spent on the ghost workers within the last political regimes of Governor Sullivan Chime is above ₦15.504 billion. Likewise, the political regime of Governor Ifeanyi Ugwuanyi within thirteen months in office has spent over ₦2,099,429,410. The phenomenal increase in the budget of the state as a result of ghost worker syndrome has undermined the delivery of the dividends of democracy in the state.

Moreover, commenting on the consequences of ghost worker menace on budget and delivery of dividends of democracy, Akeem, Momoh and Danlami, (2016) argued that there is no gain saying that ghost worker or employee fraud scheme has a heavy burden on individual citizens, victims, organizations and government. Though, the fraud scheme is observed to have financial implication on the economic performances of the state. They further delineated the likely consequences of ghost employee fraud scheme as follow:

- Growing disruption in the path of economic development
- Outrageous increase in the rate of unemployment
- Stigma of low global reputation and trust worthiness
- Governments at various levels suffer judicious utilization of allocated revenue.
- It hampers plans and actions of the victim
- It leaves corpse on management’s path; and
- Causes financial loss and untimely death for victims. (Akeem, *et al*, 2016).

The above constitute 9compendiums of the consequences of ghost employee syndrome on the economic development of the state which needs to be dressed through the concerted efforts of the government via the implementation of the integrated personnel payroll and information system and biometric technology.

However, addressing the issue of employee fraud or ghost worker syndrome, Lowers,(2014); Association of Certified Fraud Examiners,(2008) and Akeem *et al*,(2016) presented fundamental strategies for preventing ghost employee fraud.

1. The audit strategy to mask factious employee fraud:
 - a. For each person, meet the individual and inspect government issued identification.
 - b. Search for evidence of work performance
2. The audit to unmask terminated ghost employee scheme:
 - a. Compare endorsement on the check for the last payroll period to the first payroll period.
 - b. Compare hand writing on the final time report.
3. The audit strategy to unmask a pre-employment ghost employee scheme:
 - a. Compare first payment week to other relevant databases to establish a work performance data.
 - b. Interview employees to determine their recollection of their first day or week of work.
4. The audit strategy to unmask no-show ghost employee scheme:
 - a. Search for evidence of work performance
 - b. Interview co-workers
 - c. Examine access security databases for evidence of work performance.
5. The audit strategy unmask temporary employee by pass critical hiring control:
 - a. Confirm the existence of the employee through a telephone interview.
 - b. Search for evidence of work performance
 - c. Interview co-workers.
6. The audit strategy to unmask temporary employees working through agencies:

- a. Examine temporary agency payroll records to ensure that the individual was compensated and that time records support the work location.
- b. Search for evidence of work performance.
7. Audit strategy to unmask family member ghost employee scheme:
 - a. Search for evidence of work performance
8. The audit strategy to unmask unclaimed payroll check scheme:
 - a. Examine checks for false endorsements
 - b. Compare bank clearing stamps on early checks.

Theoretical Frame of Analysis

The understanding of any given phenomenon is always premised within a bounded theory for in-depth, rigorous and proper comprehension. The theoretical frame work for this paper is premised and anchored on the Marxist theory of post colonial state. This theory was made popular by the works of Alavi(1979,1972); Ake(1985,2000); Onimode(1988); Ekwewe(1985) and Ahluwalia(2001). According to Agagu (2008); Alavi(1972) they premised the theory on the historical specificity of societies; and this specificity was brought about by the structural changes brought about the colonial experience. Alavi, attributed the prominence of the post-colonial state to its power of directly appropriating a very large part of the economic surplus and deploying it in bureaucratically directed economic activities in the name of promoting economic developing.

However, corroborating the above thesis, Onimode has opines the nature and character of post-colonial state as:

“the nature of colonial disengagement from most of Africa and the third world generally ensured that the post-colonial state would become a neo-colonial state in order to preserve the same, basic colonial relationships of domination and exploitation. Theorizing about the post-colonial state in Africa is, therefore, anchored to the education of; the state in the contexts on neo-colonialism, the basic underdevelopment of the post-colonial economics, the processes of class formations and the issue of the relative autonomy of the state in performing its theoretical function”(Onimode,1988).

Deducing from the Marxist theory of post-colonial state one can easily appreciate that the state and its instruments and agencies had been commodified for selfish appropriation. The political leaders and highly placed public service use their positions of authority to recruit personnel whose identification remains unknown. The monies in the form of salaries and other entitlement for the ghost workers are siphoned. Therefore state in the post colonial is corrupt, stupid and selfish. The corrupt tendencies had forced the elites to exploit the state of its resources that would have been used to provide basic necessities and safety nets for her citizens. No wonder, Marx regards the state as the vessel for the appropriation of public treasury into private pockets.

Hypotheses

The under stated hypotheses are put forward for empirical investigation:

- i. The implementation of the integrated personnel payroll and information system has implicated the payroll frauds in Enugu State.
- ii. The Enugu State government has utilized the integrated personnel payroll and information system in planning and budgeting.

A research design as a comprehensive plan for data collection is a blue print for empirical research aimed at answering specific research questions or testing specific hypotheses. The paper adopted one group pre test post-test design. It is the design for comparing of two phenomena from the population. The scores obtained from the two separate measurements are compared, the difference in the scores are then attributed to the independent variable (Omeh,2017).

The one group pre-test post-test design is represented as; $O_1 \times O_2$ where;

O_1 = First observation

X= Independent Variable

O_2 = Second Observation (Leege and Francis,1974).

Method of Data Collection

The paper utilizes both the documentary and survey methods of data collection. Field observational and the qualitative techniques were adequately utilized. The researchers administered validated instrument to the respondents who were left alone to respond to the questionnaire. We instructed the respondents to read and study the instructions on the instruments thoroughly before responding to the questions. The research collected the responded instrument for purpose of data analysis as soon as the respondents were through with the questionnaire. As a result of the manageability of the population of study, the process of data collection did not exceed two weeks and five days (19 days).

Population and Sample

The population as a well conceivable elements, subject or observation relates to a particular phenomenon of interest to the researcher. Thus, the population of this study comprises of all public service of Enugu State who are still engaged. The total population of the public service of the state is 18,334 staff strength (Okoye;2010). This comprises of the offices of Governor, Deputy Governor, and Secretary to Enugu State government and head of service plus twenty eight (28) ministries. The distribution of questionnaire is based on one local government from each senatorial zone, that is Igbo Eze North (Enugu North Senatorial zone), Isi-Uzo (Enugu-East), and Udi (Enugu West Senatorial Zone).

In choosing the sample size for this study, we utilized Taro Yamane's formulae. Yaro's formulae is given by

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}; \text{ where}$$

N = Population size

n = sample size

e = Error margin at 5% or 0.05 level of significance.

But, N = 18,334

e = 0.05

Mathematically,

$$n = \frac{18,334}{1 + 18,334(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{18,334}{1 + 18,334(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{18,334}{1 + 45.835}$$

$$n = \frac{18,334}{46.84}$$

$$n = 391.47$$

$$n \cong 391$$

Method of Data Analysis

The research employed both qualitative and quantitative methods quantitatively; data collected were analyzed using decision mean, frequency and percentages. Also bench mark of 2.50 and above was established as the acceptance region and scores below the bench mark were rejected as decision mean.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

The presentation of data is aimed at analyzing the information gathered from the field survey based on the schedule questionnaire. The data represent the opinions of the respondents on the research questions as administered to them. The data were presented in two sections as were contained in the validate instrument. Section "A" is based on the personal information of the respondents, while section "B" is based on the questions drafted from the research questions. The instrument was designed in four point rating scale of Strongly agree (SA), Agree (A), Strongly Disagree (SD) and Disagree (D) to ascertain the degree of opinions of the respondent.

Section A: Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents

Personal Information:

Presentation of the Sex of the Respondents.

Variable	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Male	134	34.27
Female	257	65.73
Total	391	100:00

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

The above table shows that a total of 391 respondents, male constitute 134 representing 34.27% and the female, 65.73% of the total sample.

Presentation of Age Groups of Respondents.

Variables	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
20yrs – 29yrs	63	16.10
30yrs – 39yrs	81	20.72
40yrs – 49yrs	93	23.79
50yrs – 59yrs	71	18.16
60yrs – above	83	21.23
Total	391	100.00

Field Survey, 2017

The above table presents the age groups of the respondents. 16.10% representing 63 respondents were within the age group of 20-29yrs, 20.72% representing 81 respondents were within the age group of 30-39years. Also, 23.79 representing 93 respondents were within the age group of 40-49 years. The 71 respondents which represent 18.16% falls within the age group of 50-59years and 21.23% representing 83 respondents fall within the age group of 60 years and above.

Presentation of Marital Status.

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Single	60	15.35
Married	240	61.38
Divorced	50	12.78
Widow/Widowed	41	10.49
Total	391	100.00

Source: Field Survey, 2017

The table above presents a hypothetical analysis of the marital status of the respondents. From the table, 15.35%, 61.38% represent the sampled population of single and married with 60 and 240 respondents respectively. Also, 12.78% representing 50 respondents falls under the divorced and 41 respondents constituting 10.49% represents the widow/widower.

Presentation of Education Qualifications of the Respondents.

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
FSLC	36	9.20
SSCE	139	35.55
OND/NCE	102	26.09
1 ST DEGREE	85	21.74
MASTER & OTHERS	29	7.42
TOTAL	391	100:00

Source: Field Survey, 2017

The table below presents the educational qualifications of the sampled population. Thirty six (36) respondents representing 9.20% obtained First School Leaving Certificate (FLSC), One hundred and thirty nine (139) representing 35.55% obtained Senior Secondary Certificate Examination. Also, one hundred and two (102) respondents

representing 26.09% obtained Ordinary National Diploma (OND) and Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE), while eight-five (85) respondents representing 21.74% and twenty nine (29) representing 7.42% obtained their first degree, master and others respectively.

The above table is an aggregate of the two research questions posed by the researchers in the study of the relationships of integrated personnel payroll and information system and the ghost workers syndrome in Enugu State. However, questions were integrated based on items. In item one, Hundred and Forty One (141) which represents 36.06% of the sampled population strongly agreed that IPPIS is a modern technique that ensures a centrally and harmonized data of workers. On the other hand, one hundred and fifty seven (157), seventy four (74) and ninety representing 40.15%, 18.93% and 4.86% respectively represent agreed, strongly disagreed and disagree respectively. The decision is 3.07, we accepted the resolution that the integrated personnel payroll and information system is a modern technique that ensures a centrally and harmonized data of workers.

S/N	ITEM/VARIABLE	STRONGLY AGREE (SA)	AGREE (A)	STRONGLY DISAGREE (SD)	DISAGREE	MEAN	DECISION
1.	The integrated personnel payroll and informal system (IPPIS) is a modern technique that ensures a centrally and harmonized data of workers	141	157	74	19	3.07	Accept
2.	The menace of ghost workers has been curtailed following the implementation of IPPIS	192	103	58	38	3.15	Accept
3.	There is an element of manipulation of the IPPIS by the administrative cadre	203	97	39	52	3.15	Accept
4.	Lacks of state investments were as a result of chunks of monies dwindled in paying ghost workers.	163	189	11	28	3.25	Accept
5.	IPPIS and computerization ensure the sanity of the state public service	127	183	36	45	3.00	Accept
6.	The implementation of IPPIS has fastened other techniques like Biometric technology	261	79	33	18	3.49	Accept
7.	The state has utilized the data through IPPIS in its planning and budgeting	261	77	36	17	2.96	Accept
8.	Corruption has eaten deep in to the states budget by its public service	325	45	17	8	3.78	Accept
9.	The personnel that exceeded the computerization and verification exercise were political.	134	29	172	56	2.62	Accept
10.	The state government has adopt the modern system of planning and budgeting based on the records of IPPIS	194	87	69	41	3.13	Accept
11.	The non-implementation of IPPIS and computerization in the past has forced the state government to have staggered planning and budgeting	221	97	49	24	3.32	Accept
12.	The state has publicized the authentic number of ghost workers after the computerization and verification exercises.	38	43	227	83	2.09	Reject

Furthermore, item two reveals that one hundred and ninety two (192), one hundred and three (103), fifty-eight (58) and thirty eight (38) which represent 49.10%, 26.34%, 14.83% and 9.72% respectively constitute strongly agreed, agreed, strongly disagreed and disagreed on the menace of ghost workers and how it has been curtailed through the implementation of IPPIS. The decision mean is 3.15 then we accepted that the menace of ghost worker has been curtailed following the implementation of integrated personnel payroll and information system.

In item three, out of the sampled population of Three Hundred and ninety one (391), two hundred and three (203), ninety-seven (97), thirty nine and fifty two (52) representing 51.92%, 24.81%, 9.97% and 13.30% strongly agreed, agreed, strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively. The decision mean is 3.15. Therefore, we accepted that there was an element of manipulation by the administrative cadre in the implementation of IPPIS and verification exercises.

In item four, one hundred and sixty three (163) representing 41.69% strongly agreed, one hundred and eighty nine (189) representing 48.34% agreed, eleven representing 2.81% strongly disagreed and twenty eight representing 7.16% disagreed that lack of state investments were as a result of chunks of monies dwindled in paying ghost workers. Since the decision mean is 3.25 we accepted that lack of state investments were as a result of chunks of monies dwindled in paying ghost workers.

Also in item five, one hundred twenty seven (127) respondents representing 32.48% , one hundred eighty three (183) representing 46.80%, thirty six (36) respondents representing 9.21% and forty five (45) respondents representing 11.51% of the sampled population strongly agreed, agreed, strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively that IPPIS and computerization ensure the sanity of the state's public service and since decision mean is 3.00, we accepted the decision rule that integrated personnel payroll and information system and computerization ensure the sanity of the state's public service.

Furthermore, interpreting the item six, we have that out of three hundred and ninety one sampled population, two hundred and sixty one (66.75%), seventy nine (20.20%), thirty three (8.44%) and eighteen (4.60%) of the population strongly agreed, agree, strongly disagree and disagreed respectively that the implementation of IPPIS has fastened other techniques like biometric technology. We accepted the decision rule since the decision mean is 3.49.

In item seven, two hundred and sixty one (261) representing 66.75% strongly agreed, seventy seven (77) representing 19.69% agreed, thirty six (36) representing 9.21% strongly disagreed and seventeen (17) representing 4.35% disagreed that the state has utilized the data through IPPIS in its planning and budgeting respectively. Then, since the decision mean is 2.96, we accepted the decision rule. However, in item eight, three hundred and twenty five (325) respondents representing 83.12% strongly agreed, forty five (45) representing 11.51% agreed, seventeen (17) representing 2.05% disagreed respectively that corruption has eaten deep into the state's budget by its public service.

Moreover, in item nine, we have that out of the sampled population, one hundred and thirty four representing 34.27% strongly agreed, twenty nine (29) representing 7.42% agreed, one hundred seventy two (172) representing 43.99% strongly disagreed and fifty six (56) representing 14.32% disagreed respectively that the personnel that executed the computerization and verification exercise were political. Then, for the fact the decision mean is 2.62, we accepted that the personnel that executed the computerization and verification exercise were political. On the item ten, we have that out three hundred and ninety one sampled population, One hundred and ninety four (194) representing 49.62% strongly agreed, eighty seven (87) representing 22.25% agreed, sixty nine (69) representing 17.65% strongly disagreed and forty one (41) representing 10.49% disagreed respectively that the state government has adopted the modern system of planning and budgeting based in the records of IPPIS. But, since the decision mean is 3.13, we accepted that the state government has adopted the modern system of planning and budgeting based on the records of IPPIS.

Furthermore, in item eleven, we have that out of the sampled population, two hundred and twenty one (221) representing 56.52% strongly agreed, ninety seven (97) representing 24.53% agreed, forty nine (49) representing 12.53% strong disagreed and twenty four (24) representing 6.14% disagreed respectively that the non-implementation of IPPIS and computerization in the past has forced the state government to have staggered planning and budgeting. But, so far the decision mean is 3.32; we accepted that the non-implementation of IPPIS and computerization in the part has forced the state government to have experienced staggered planning and budgeting.

However in item twelve, thirty eight (38) representing 9.72% strongly agreed, forty three (43) representing 10.10% agreed, two hundred and twenty seven (227) representing 58.06% strongly disagreed and eighty three (83) representing 21.23% disagreed respectively that the state has published the authentic number of ghost workers after the computerization and verification exercise. But, for the fact the decision mean is 2.09 we rejected the decision rule that state has published the authentic number of ghost workers after the computerization and verification exercise.

Discussion of Findings

The development and progress of every human society is dependent on the potentials and ingenuity of the man to explore, overcome and control his immediate environment. The history of corruption (ghost workers syndrome) in Nigeria is strongly rooted in the over 29 years of military rule, out of 46 years of her statehood successive military regimes facilitated the wanton looting of the public treasury, decapitated institutions and free speech and instituted a secret and opaque culture in the running of government business. The result was total insecurity, poor economic management, abuse of human rights, ethnic conflict and capital flight (Ribadu, 2006).

The pattern of corruption can be said to exist whenever a power holder who is charged with doing things, who is a responsible functionary or office holder is by monetary or other rewards not legally provided for, induced to take actions which favour whoever provides the rewards and thereby does damaged to the public and its interests (Ikejian-Clark; 1995, Friedrich, 1966). However, the phenomenon and destination of corruption (Ghost worker cartel) in Enugu State has seriously been beset with pessimism, while the prospects of a successful war against it is greeted with cynicism, the scathing statement that keeping an average Nigerian from being corrupt is like keeping a goat from eating yam is rather an extreme and bizarre way to paint the picture of corruption in Nigeria (Chuta, 2004:75).

However, arresting the trending situations of ghost worker syndrome in Nigeria and Enugu State in particular calls for proactive actions with an attendant implementation of high sophisticated technology that has the tendency to securitize the data of the state's public service. Findings reveal that despite the facts that ghost worker syndrome has dealt the State seriously in the past, Enugu State has adequately adjusted to appreciate laudable and long lasting solution to the menace. The implementation of the integrated personnel payroll and information system through the process of physical verification to computerization of the data of workers has reduced the scourging tendencies of ghost workers in the public service of Enugu State.

Finally the work reveals that constant implementation of IPPIS has the capacity to re-position the state government to reduce her personnel cost and enhances scientific planning and budgeting that would help to provide the state with the capacity building in delivery dividends of democracy that will foster rapid transformation, growth and development of the State's economy.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The trending wave of ghost workers in post-colonial African societies and the attendant globalization and vagaries in the level of international market had conscripted the State from fulfilling her social obligation. In the recent times, Nigeria and Enugu State in particular had find it extremely difficult to pay her wages and salaries entitled to the workers and other needed development in other areas. This could be attributed to enormous and bloated State treasury earmarked and siphoned through the ghost worker syndrome.

However, from our findings that were analyzed it is recommended that:

1. There should be constant and time frame checks for validation of the State's public service those who had retired, dismissed, dead and resigned through the instrumentation of IPPIS.
2. The policy of whistle blowing should be encouraged in all sectors and tiers of government. The whistle blowers should also be protected by the Law.
3. The Nigeria system of prosecution of immunity as contained in the law for the protection of political office holders should be removed with an immediate effect. With the adequate removal of this immunity clause, public officers should be made open to investigation and scientific auditing should be appreciated to uncover their corrupt tendencies.
4. There is serious need to re-orient Nigerians. This is exclusive on the moralism rather diehard materialism.
5. The fourth estate realm of government should adequately prepare to report cases of corrupt practices in whatever forms. This has to be complemented through the joint efforts of the organized civil society organizations.
6. Finally, any person, group and cartel that engage in corrupt practices of ghost workers should be caused to face stiff, strict and enforceable penalties. This will help to deter others from committing same.

REFERENCES

- i. "6,280 Ghost Workers, Pensioners to face ICPC Problem in Enugu." *Vanguard News Online*, Saturday, August 5, 2017.
- ii. "How Over 6,000 Ghost Workers Defrauded Enugu Government" *Daily Post News Online*, Saturday August 9, 2017.
- iii. Adebayo, A. (2004). *Principles and Practice of Public Administration in Nigeria*. Ibadan: Spectrum Books Limited
- iv. Agagu, A.A. (2008). *The Nigerian State and the Dilemma of Citizenship Issues and Challenges*. Lagos: Policy Development and Consultant Limited.

- v. Ahluwalia, P. (2001). *Politics and Post Colonial Theory: African Inflections*. London: Routledge.
- vi. Ake, C. (2000). "The State in Contemporary Africa" in Nnoli, (ed.) *Government and Politics of Africa*. Harare: AAPS Books.
- vii. Ake, C.(1985). "The Nigerian State: Antinomies of a Periphery" in Ake, C. (ed). *The Political Economy of Nigeria*. London: Longman
- viii. Akeem, T.N., Momoh, I.Y & Danlami, J.A. (2016). "Assessment of the Variations of Ghost Employee Fraud in Nigeria: 2008-2015." *European Journal of Business and Management* 8(24)pp1-10
- ix. Alavi, H. (1972). "The Post-Colonial State" *New Left* 74, July-August
- x. Alavi, H. (1979). *Politics and State in the Third World*. London: Macmillan Press Ltd
- xi. Association of Certified Fraud Examiners, (2008). "Other Peoples Money: The Basics of Asset Misappropriation." <http://ace.com/documents/others-peoples-money-excerpt>
- xii. Bovens, M.(2005). "Analyzing and Assessing Public Accountability: A Conceptual Frame work: *European Government Papers* 6(1)"
- xiii. Chuta, S.C. (2004). "Corruption in Nigeria". Enugu: Afro Orbis Publications
- xiv. Drucker, P. (2007). "Governance". *Harvard Business Review* 45(2). Iyoha, M. and Oriakhi, D. (2002). "Explaining African Economic Growth Performance: The Case of Nigeria." *African Economic Research Consortium Project*"
- xv. Ekwewe, E. (1985). "State and Economic Development in Nigeria" in Ake, C.(ed.) *The Political Economy of Nigeria*. London: Longman.
- xvi. Eme, O.I. and Ogbechie, A. (2003). "Civil Service and Cost of Governance in Nigeria." *International Journal of Accounting Research* 1(2)
- xvii. Enakirerhi, L.I and Temile, S.O. (2017). "IPPIS in Nigeria. Challenges, Benefits and Prospects." *International Journal of Social Science and Economic Research*, 2(5) pp3491
- xviii. Eya,P.O. (2016). *Harmonizing Biometrics Registration in Nigeria: A Case of Enugu State Local Government Commission*. Unpublished BSc Project, Department of Public Administration and Local Government, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- xix. Fafowora, D. (2011). "Public Service and Cost of Governance" *The Nation*, Thursday, September 15. P52.
- xx. Fluvian, G. (2006). "The Rising Cost of Governance." *African Journal of Public Administration* 22(9) pp. 41-46
- xxi. Fredrich, C. (1966). "Political Pathology." *Political Quarterly* 37
- xxii. Hall, L. and Torrington, D.P. (1998). *The Human Resources Function: The Dynamic Change and Development*. London: Financial Times, Pitman Publishing
- xxiii. Idris,H., and Audu,J.S. (2015). "Integrated Personnel Payroll and Information System: Panacea for Ghost Workers Syndrome in Nigeria." *International Journal of Social Science and Economic Research*, 2 (5) pp348
- xxiv. Ikejiani – Clark, M. (1995). "Corruption in Nigeria" in Onuoha, J.I. & Ozioko, J.O.C. (eds). *Contemporary Issues in Social Sciences*. Enugu: Acena Publishers.

- xxv. *Leege, D.C. and Francis, W. (1974). Political Research. New York: Basic Books.Inc*
- xxvi. *Lowers, M.(2014). "Protecting Against Ghost Employee Fraud" <http://lowersriskgroup.com/blog>. Retrieved on 03/08/2017.*
- xxvii. *Mede, (2016). "Nigeria's Experience with identity Systems for Civil Service Reforms." A Paper Presented at the Africa Annual Meeting Held in Rwanda.*
- xxviii. *Ogunna, A.E.C. (1999). Public Administration in Nigeria: Theory and Practice. Owerri: Versatile Publishers*
- xxix. *Okoye, R.C. (2010). The Effects of Retrenchment on the Morale of Workers: A Study of Enugu State Civil Service. Unpublished BSc Project, Department of Management, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.*
- xxx. *Omeh,P.H.(2017).Contributory Pension Scheme and Management of Retirement Benefits in the University of Nigeria:2013-2016. Unpublished MSc Thesis, Department of Political Science, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.*
- xxxi. *Onimode, B.(1988). A Politics of the African Crisis. London: Zed Books Ltd.*
- xxxii. *Onuegbu, C.H. (2015). "Urgent Need for More Elaborate Audit of Government Payrolls." The News Daily Online Tuesday, August 1, 2015.*
- xxxiii. *Ribadu, M.U. (2006). "Nigeria's Struggle with Corruption" A Paper Presented to US Congressional House Committee on International Development, Washington, DC May 8, 2006.*
- xxxiv. *The Menace of Ghost Workers "Daily Sun News Online, Saturday, February 13, 2016.*
- xxxv. *Uzochukwu, M. (2016). "Unemployment in Nigeria and Solutions" <http://hubpages.com/business/unemployment-in-Nigeria-and-solutions>. Retired on 23/08/2017*